

CALLIGRAPHY

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Abstract: This article provides information about the history of calligraphy, Arabic script and the art of calligraphy, the emergence of the art of calligraphy in Central Asia, the formation of calligraphy and the discovery of new forms of writing in the Arabic alphabet, and their names.

Key words: calligraphy, calligraphy, printing, real script, Kufic script.

Introduction.

As you know, the formation of a letter is a complex process and involves hard work. Handwriting should be as individual as possible, but it should be as legible as possible. Not everyone remembers how this important skill was developed. Gradually, adults notice a serious deterioration in handwriting. If this is clear, it is necessary to download the recipe for correction of handwriting of adults, because the consequences of such a conclusion can be very sad.

A person cannot even correct a short text. Poor handwriting is mainly used to judge the author's organizational and executive ability. At the slightest emotional stress, handwriting deteriorates, and it is necessary not only to improve it, but also to normalize the mental state. Can't even remember when the handwriting got worse. Many people think that this happens during training, when they have to write a lot and fast. The opposite situation is also not mysterious, that is, it is impossible to understand when a person begins to write clearly and beautifully.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Calligraphy, calligraphy is the art of writing, book copying, and the profession of creating books of architectural structures and works of art. Occurred as a result of the entry. Especially, due to the wide spread of Arabic writing, the development of calligraphy accelerated. In the East, including in Central Asia, before the advent of printing, calligraphers were engaged in making manuscript books and reproducing their copies.

The importance of clear handwriting cannot be overstated. A text made up of incomprehensible symbols and slurs cannot be taken seriously. The way characters are written depends on several factors. It is difficult to determine the reasons for its deterioration or improvement. Scientists are trying to determine the role of hereditary genes, persistence in the classroom, conscientiousness of the teacher. These are just a few conditions, all of which are very difficult to define.

It is much more accurate to determine what each person's handwriting is talking about. If you want to change your destiny, try to change it. In order for adults to create understandable texts, we solved this difficult task and developed special recipes for adults to improve handwriting. They are bought by those who decide to correct the spelling of letters and numbers, improve writing, make it simple and understandable.

Before the advent of printing, calligraphers were engaged in the work of preparing books and reproducing their copies. Calligraphers' groups were organized in the palaces under the presence of some officials. For example, Mirzo Boysungur gathered a group of 40 calligraphers in his palace. One such calligrapher was Sultanali Mashhadi, who was born in 1432 and died in 1520. He is known by honorary nicknames such as "*qiblatul kuttab*" and "*sultanul-khattotain*". He was also no stranger to poetry criticism.

The purpose of good and beautiful writing is not only to make it easy to read, but also to give the reader aesthetic pleasure, to make the writing beautiful and beautiful. As we mentioned, the art of calligraphy spread widely among the peoples of the Near East on the basis of the Arabic script, the six series of Arabic script - suls, naskh, muhaqqaq, rayhan, tawq'e' and riq'a' writings laid the foundation for the Arabic calligraphy art. The method of calligraphy depends on the type of writing. Calligraphy had its own theoretical and practical laws, which were strictly adhered to by the connoisseurs. The theory of calligraphy was founded by the famous calligraphers of the 10th and 11th centuries, Abu Ali Muhammad and All Ibni Hilal. They developed the tradition of Yaqut Mustasimi theoretically.

Results:

Excellent stylistic material written in a special font is designed for those who aim to achieve fast, beautiful, adult handwriting. In teaching children this knowledge, the traditional school has long followed two main principles. Effective learning, in the first of them, is not the goal. It is more important to structure the learning process, explaining to the students why they need to go through the signs instead of trying to achieve their goal.

Writing fast, but writing beautifully is difficult, on the contrary, in the hands of adults. You should be given some responsibility to control your actions. And, of course, it is very important not to back down and strive to achieve the goal through regular and tireless training. The history of calligraphy is inextricably linked with writing instruments. Today, ancient tools exist simultaneously with a ballpoint pen, a felt-tip pen, a synthetic brush, but flutes continue to occupy one of the leading positions.

A wide-brimmed pen, even in inexperienced hands, ensures the correct ratio of the width of the lines in the letters, and beginners quickly learn the basics of handwritten font. This publication emphasizes extensive writing.

Discussion:

Calligraphers worked as a group in palaces, under the presence of certain masters. In particular, more than 40 calligraphers, along with painters, painters and other masters, were engaged in preparing manuscript books and repairing those that had become unusable in the library established by the Timurid prince Boysungur Mirza in Herat. Many books on the art of calligraphy state that there are 10 basic styles of letters.

Before the spread of Arabic script in Central Asia, there were different writing systems. Kufic writing, which is one of the ancient writings, has been preserved in the decoration of many architectural and other monuments. In particular, the Osman Qur'an, which is kept in the religious office of the Muslims of Uzbekistan, was also copied in this Kufi.

Copying of the Qur'an was done with naskh, tawqah was used for writing orders and decrees, and riq'a was used for writing letters. In addition to these, there were amulets, dust, shajari, tugro and other writing methods. From the 15th century, the nastaq letter was used in the copying of books. Calligraphy was highly developed in Central Asia during the Timurid,

Shaibani and last dynasties. During the time of Amir Timur, Maulana Shamsuddin Munshi, composer and calligrapher Oltun were very famous.

Calligraphy has long been developed in Central Asia. Calligraphy is the art of beautiful and correct writing, the profession of book copying. The history of calligraphy is closely related to the development of writing and the pen, the main weapon of literature. After the appearance of writing and the pen, special people began to study calligraphy. Especially after the spread of Arabic writing, calligraphy developed widely.

Summary:

In conclusion, it should be said that the art of calligraphy, as we mentioned, was based on certain laws and requirements, and these requirements required mathematical precision. The art of calligraphy based on the hexadecimal system chose the circle shape as the norm. Within this circle, a triangle, square and pentagon with equal sides are drawn, and the pattern of letters is made from it. For each letter, diamond-shaped dots from top to bottom were used. The amount of points has been changed depending on the types of records. For example, eight dots were required for muhaqqaq script, seven dots for suls script and six dots for tawqe' script.

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